

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF THE ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The article reveals the theoretical aspects of the analysis of economic systems. The economic system is a complex, nonlinear, dynamic system that goes through various changes. Changes can be related to natural evolution, as well as to external influences and crises. The issues of theoretical and practical analysis of economic systems have been widely studied in modern scientific literature. However, the issue of analyzing the economic system of the state in its development (movement) remains insufficiently investigated. The basis for writing this article is the achievements of modern scientists in the analysis of economic systems, management theory and the basics of systems research. The article systematizes the theoretical aspects of the analysis of economic systems, identifies the main difficulties of this analysis, and suggests ways to solve them.

Keywords: system research; theory of systems; analysis of economic systems; economic management.

Introduction

In modern economic thought, analysis is considered as one of the management functions. Such famous scientists as V.N. Shimov, A.I. Korotkevich, I.V. Novikova, Yu.M. Yasinsky, I.V. Blauberg, E.G. Yudin, A. Schueller, H.G. Krusselberg (for more details in the publication [1]), V.N. Kalinin [2], D.A. Novikova [3], V.A. Borodenko [4], V.A. Besekersky, E.P. Popova [5], V.N. Afanasyeva [6], E.M. Borodin, K.N. Borodina [7], B.S. Dobronets, O.A. Popova [8], A.P. Vlasova [9], O.V. Folka, I.F. Ivashkina [10], N.V. Spiridonova [11] made a great contribution to the development of the principles of the functioning of the economic system, approaches to the study of the economic system, the theory of management and system analysis, and the theoretical analysis of economic systems. However, the issues of the analysis of economic systems as complex, dynamic, multiconnected, multiparametric and nonlinear systems are insufficiently studied. The solution of these issues will contribute to improving the efficiency of the management of the economic system of the state.

Results and discussion

Consider the concept of a system – it is "an integral set of interrelated and interacting elements with properties that are not reduced to the properties of these elements and are not derived from them" [2, p. 22]. This thesis reflects the complexity of the analysis of the economic system. The economic system of the state includes many subsystems that have a certain independence. "A subsystem of a system is a set of its elements, which is itself a system" [2, p. 22]. All these elements are in constant dynamics of their change (development).

Consider the concept of economic analysis – "it is the identification of economic patterns from the facts of economic reality and their study in parts" [12, p. 4]. The analysis of economic systems covers the following areas:

1) monitoring and recording of qualitative and quantitative parameters of the system functioning;

2) the study of macroeconomic processes and phenomena in their relationship to each other;

3) identification and measurement (evaluation) of positive and negative factors that affect the functioning of the economic system;

4) identification of trends, proportions and patterns of functioning and development of economic systems;

5) selection of methods and parameters for the analysis of various structural elements of the economic system;

6) interpretation of the results obtained;

7) generalization of world experience;

8) development of directions for improving the functioning of economic systems;

9) substantiation of plans, forecasts, assessment of the fulfillment of planned indicators, etc.

The complexities of analyzing economic systems include the need to study:

➤ the nonlinearity of the system and its individual elements;

➤ multiple connectivity of system elements;

➤ a multiparameter system;

➤ explicit and implicit cause-and-effect relationships;

➤ unobservable parameters of the economy, an assessment of the "a priori unknown state of the system based on indirect, external data and signs" [2, p. 37];

➤ conditionally free and forced movements and reactions of the system;

➤ inertia of the system;

➤ temporary delay in the system's response to management impact;

➤ the transition characteristics of the system upon reaching its target (forecast) state.

The substantiation of these difficulties in the analysis of economic systems was the methodological basis for substantiating the directions for their solution.

The *main difficulty of analyzing economic systems is its non-linearity*. Therefore, in order to implement the basic principle of control systems and describe the

mechanism of its functioning, it is necessary to transform a nonlinear system into a linear one. For this purpose, a linearized mathematical apparatus can be used. An economic system can include both nonlinear and linear subsystems, which determines objective differences in the mathematical tools used to build models; values (parameters) "time constants" that reflect the system's ability to respond to changes. Thus, we can identify three main areas of analysis of the economic system of the state as a nonlinear system: 1) analysis of linear elements (subsystems); 2) analysis of nonlinear elements (subsystems) that can be studied as linear systems. In this case, the conditions and mathematical tools for the transition to linearity are determined; 3) analysis of the fundamental nonlinearities of the system, i.e. those subsystems that cannot be approximated by linear dependencies.

An important place in solving the complexities of analyzing a large number of relationships between the elements of an economic system (multiconnection of system elements) and analyzing a large number of groups of economic indicators (a multiparametric system) is occupied by: identification of the distinctive features and properties of the system; classification of the system's reactions depending on the types of management impact; identification of the relationship of the reaction with the stable properties of the economic system. The quality of the study of the initial state of the economic system depends on the objectivity and accuracy of: assessment of the impact of input signals (strength, speed, delay time, etc.); calculation of the system's response to management impact; justification of forecast indicators of system development.

The basis for the study of these difficulties is the identification of the necessary analysis parameters. To study the multiple connectivity of the elements of the economic system, it is necessary:

1) to investigate and identify all types of stable cause-and-effect relationships, as well as the factors that influence them;

2) to identify the cause-and-effect relationships that have lost their relevance, as well as the factors that influenced them;

3) to identify and identify new (unstable) cause-and-effect relationships that have emerged as a result of the objective development of the economic system or as a result of changes in world markets.

The indicators (parameters) of the analysis of the economic system may vary depending on the priority development goals of the state. Such goals may include: economic growth, full employment of the population, stable price levels, economic efficiency, maintaining the foreign trade balance [13, pp. 20-21], etc. All this determines the complexity and variety of parameters of the analysis of the country's economic system.

Indicators (parameters) should ensure the objectivity of reflection and registration of all processes and phenomena in the economy, as well as a qualitative assessment of the interaction of the economic system with the environment [14]. The parameters (indicators) may include: indicators that characterize "the causes and factors of growth, the degree of balance of the economy, the type of reproduction" [11, p. 54]; parameters

of macroeconomic regulation: "aggregate demand and aggregate supply, unemployment and inflation; the general level of prices and incomes, economic growth" [15, p. 54]. 5] and others.; The parameters that characterize the social results of the functioning of the economy are: "the level and dynamics of real incomes, income differentiation ... the quality of consumption ... the development of the socio-cultural sphere" [11, p. 54], etc.

The selected indicators (parameters) of the analysis should allow an assessment of individual structural elements of economic systems. These elements can be: sectors of the economy and their corresponding institutional units in the context of economic activities; spheres of the economy; elements of the system in the context of producers of tangible and intangible goods; natural and material resources; levels of interaction of subjects of economic relations (international level, macro level, meso level, micro level [1]); various macroeconomic proportions between the elements systems, etc.

Description of explicit and hidden cause-and-effect relationships. The analysis of the necessary economic parameters should combine the results of the achievements of economic science and the empirically identified relationships, including the identified relationships with the parameters of socio-economic development of the country. The result of the interaction of the elements of the economic system are various economic processes and phenomena that also need to be analyzed. An integral part of this component of the analysis is the development of methodological tools for assessing the synergetic effect. To assess the synergetic effect, it is proposed: 1) to identify the common peaks of the elements (processes, phenomena) of the economic system. These elements must be represented (described) in the form of integral indicators; 2) using mathematical tools, describe the edges (networks) that connect the vertices. The edges reflect the horizontal and vertical types of connections between the elements of the system.

Equally important is the *analysis of the "unobservable parameters"* of the economy. The main difficulty is related to "estimating the state of a dynamic system (usually inaccessible to direct measurement) at a given time based on recording (direct fixation, measurement) and studying the reaction of the system" [2, p. 36]. The main question is: how to distinguish a system object from a non-system one? The appendix to our study shows how to distinguish economic processes occurring in an unobserved economy from non-systemic (chaotic) manifestations based on the stable properties of the economic system. The process is based on: empirically identified proportions of macroeconomic indicators; developed methodological tools for analyzing the unobserved economy. Methodological tools should allow to determine the current state of the system by explicit and weak (hidden) signals. The current state of the system is characterized by certain qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the functioning of the economy.

Identification of conditionally free and forced movements and reactions of the system. The solution to this complexity includes the identification, analysis and

evaluation of conditionally free movements and reactions of the system ("in the absence of control action" [2, p. 31]) and forced movements and reactions of the system ("in the presence of control action" [2, p. 31]), as well as their integral assessment. This complexity is a consequence of the non-linearity of the equations that describe the structural elements of the economic system, which determines the diversity of the number of states of the system.

The main methodological components of the task are: registration and assessment of conditionally free movements (state changes) of the economic system; registration and assessment of forced movements (state changes) of the economic system; identification and classification of input conditionally free signals (impacts); identification and classification of input control actions; identification and classification of system reactions to input conditionally free signals (effects); identification and classification of system reactions to input control effects; the construction of a system of differential equations, which will allow to evaluate the change in the integrative properties of the system due to various types of impacts.

The practical implementation of this component is based on:

1) the constructed "model of the disturbing component (description of interaction with the environment)" (for more details, see publication [16]);

2) recognition of the fact that the economic system never has absolutely free movement. The economic system is always in constant interaction with various subjects and objects. The only question is whether these entities and objects have an impact on the economic system, and if they do, what is their strength and direction. The movement (change, development) of the economic system can be free in some directions and forced in others. This combination leads the economic system to a certain final state, which must be described using integral equations;

3) the study of environmental types: deterministic, stochastic, targeted, unknown [2, p. 32]);

4) identification of types of connections;

5) research of types and types of control actions (retrospective analysis; analysis of types and types of control actions available (implemented) for management in the current and future (forecast) time periods);

6) assessment of the disturbing effect and justification of the type of regulator (mathematical tools): proportional, integral, differential, and their derivatives. The system's regulator allows you to monitor the current state of the economic system, monitor changes in the set qualitative and quantitative parameters of the system, and identify their deviations;

7) identification and evaluation of the types of feedback between the system and the disturbing component (impact). Positive feedback is a relationship in which the system's response leads to a change in the input signal that further deviates from the initial state of the system. Negative feedback is a type of feedback in which the system's response leads to a change in the input signal that counteracts the initial change. This connection reduces the impact on the system and makes it more resistant to accidental changes in parameters;

8) determining the desired system responses to management impacts. The reactions of the economic system can be: various economic and social consequences; changing economic proportions; increasing the efficiency of the economy; increasing consumer demand; increasing the volume of domestic and external investments; increasing the stability of the system; increasing the birth rate; reducing mortality and others;

9) evaluation of the "increment of control action" – in control theory, it is commonly understood as an increment of an argument that gives an increment of a function (a change in the state of the system at time t_n). The state of the system described by the functions before (at point t_0) and after (at point t_n) the action will allow us to obtain the velocity (first order of the differential equation) or acceleration (second order of the differential equation) of the "increment of the control action". The results obtained will be the basis for answering the following two questions: what should be the frequency of the same type of management impact; what is the time point of the beginning of a new type of management impact;

10) assessment of the resilience of the economic system to targeted and non-targeted impacts. The basis for determining the level of stability of an economic system is the feedback principle: if the response of the system $Y(t)$ to the input effect $X(t)$ reaches the expected value with the specified quality indicators (parameters, properties), then such a system can be considered stable. The necessary elements of this component are: determination of function extremes; identification of aperiodic links and their degrees; determination of the elasticity of the system; identification of bifurcation points.

The construction of this component is based on a constructive description of the structure of the economic system, which should answer the question of how to form a system. Structurally, any system can be represented through a set of system elements that include: input (managerial and non-targeted impact); management object (economic system); output (system response to managerial and non-targeted impact). The practical implementation of the entry and exit of the system can be carried out through information, regulatory regulation, changes in the business conditions of economic entities, changes in the volume and quality of resources, changes in logistics, and others. An important place in this process is occupied by retrospective analysis and analysis of "reachability sets" [2, p. 35]. The result of the component is a classification of cause-and-effect relationships that contribute to achieving the set goals for the development of the country's economic system.

Inertia of the system. According to the law of inertia, the economic system retains its current state and movement characteristics in the absence of any external forces. This law is associated with the complexity of changing the characteristics (qualities, properties) of the system. The main methodological task is to assess the inertia of the system and calculate the "time constant" of management impact.

A temporary delay in the system's response to management impact. Lag time (in systems theory) is the repetition of an input signal exactly in its shape and magnitude, but with some delay (shift) in time. This

component is of great importance for assessing the sustainability of the economic system, as well as for assessing the system's response to the impact.

The main methodological objectives of the component are: implementation of a continuous monitoring process; objective registration of indicators of the input effect on the system and the types of reactions that correspond to them; calculation of the delay time of the system's response to random (chaotic) and targeted (managerial) effects; assessment of the competitiveness of the economic system; assessment of the system's exposure to external influences; study of undiminished fluctuations.

Transitional characteristics of the system upon reaching its target (forecast) state. The transient characteristic of a system, in systems theory, represents the reaction of a dynamic system to an external influence applied to it from the moment of application of this influence to a certain steady-state value in the time domain. The study of transients is an important step in the process of analyzing the dynamic properties of an economic system (for more details, see [17]). The main methodological task of the component is to assess the level (values, parameters) of acceptable transitional characteristics of the system at different time stages.

Various indicators can be used to analyze the transitional characteristics of the system, for example: the growth rate of indicators of sustainable economic development (gross domestic product, gross value added, gross national income, gross savings, net lending, and others); various structural indicators: output structures, primary income distribution, sources of financing capital transactions, and others; quantitative proportions between macroeconomic indicators; inflation rate and others.

If the chosen management law does not fully ensure the set quality indicators for the development of the economic system, then corrective links must be introduced.

Conclusion

The economic system is a complex, dynamic, multiconnected, multiparametric system. These characteristics determine the complexity of its analysis. The article identifies the main difficulties of analyzing economic systems, which are related to: the nonlinearity of the system; the multiple connectivity of the system elements; a large number of observed parameters; the presence of explicit and hidden cause-and-effect relationships; the presence of unobservable parameters; the integral effect on the system of conditionally free and forced movements; inertia of the system; time delays in the system's response to the impact; determining the acceptable transient characteristics of the system. Solving these difficulties will allow: to increase the accuracy of the forecast assessment of economic development; to identify problems of the functioning of the economic system in a timely manner; to optimize the types of management impact; to achieve the necessary system response to various types of impacts; to reduce the complexity of the system; to develop corrective methodological tools for possible overregulation of the system; to substantiate the marginal conditions of the function-

ing of the economic system in a given time interval; improve system performance indicators such as speed, accuracy, stability (reliability) of the system.

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